

WORKING PAPER

A systematic literature review on gender discussion in Spain

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1. Introduction

Advances in the field of gender equality in Spain have been accompanied by enhanced academic research on gender issues. Among others, an increasing number of publications about gender issues have been featured in social sciences academic papers, conferences and book reviews. Some of the topics and areas of interest within this field of study include gender violence, gender and family roles, education, work-life balance, masculinities' studies and sexual identities. These themes represent the deep transformations in the position of Spanish gender-based needs and demands during the last decades; which appears to bring new challenges for theoretical and empirical development in gender research.

This working paper aims to provide an overview of the results obtained in a literature review process developed over the Spanish scholarship focused on gender discussions between 2007 and 2023. It provides insights into the particularities of the local context regarding the most meaningful theoretical concepts and gender perspectives, the evolution of the main issues as well as those public policies related to gender which need to be advanced.

2. Analytical Approach

To conduct our systematic literature review on feminist permeation in the Spanish context, we followed a funnel approach to identify locations and trends of gender thought. In this sense, we first drew a list of sixty relevant Spanish institutions focused on gender studies. Then, we detected the main outlets belonging to these institutions, as library repositories and gender studies journals. Additionally, because of their relevance in the Spanish social sciences, we added journals not specialized in gender, yet with several meaningful articles that address gender issues from a political scientist and sociologic perspective. Finally, we identified benchmark authors who are experts in sub-fields of gender studies. Following this search mechanism, we collected all publications in Spanish and English language, between 2007 and 2023, which included relevant keywords for our interests (gender, mother, wom[a/e]n, masculin[e/ity/ies], femnin[e/ity/ies], [fe]male, women's rights, sexuality, feminist, reproductive rights). After reaching saturation, this search criterion yielded an initial sample of 146 publications. All contributions were then

subjected to an inspection to select those ones who accomplished three conditions: address gender-based needs, focus on the Spanish context and, thirdly, coming from a feminist perspective/ masculinity literature. Thus, our final sample consisted of 75 publications (see Figure 1).

Of the 75 contributions scrutinized, 51 are empirical, 23 are theoretical and one is a legal case study. Regarding the methodology of those empirical, 44 are qualitative, five employ quantitative techniques and three of them combined mixed methods. In terms of language, the majority of the them are in Spanish, we gathered only fourteen publications in English and one in Galician, one of the official regional languages in Spain.

Figure 1. Selection process

3. Central gender concepts, theoretical perspectives and gender coverage in the Spanish context

In Spain, the evolution of gender research, concepts and theoretical perspectives has been influenced by political and socioeconomic historical events associated with policy-making guiding principles (Gartzia y Lopez-Zafra 2014). Until 1975, Spain was under the regime of a conservative authoritarian dictatorship headed by Francisco Franco whereby Spanish women’s rights were diminished and the role of women as mothers and housewives was placed at the center of the regime’s ideals in order to preserve tradition through a clear gender division of labour (Morcillo 2000). During this time, scientific research received limited attention (Jiménez-Contreras et al. 2003).

Notwithstanding, advances toward gender equality occurred relatively quickly after 1975. The increasing feminist movement and the influence of more progressive policies established by the central State led to relevant advances in women’s rights and social status, including, for instance, changes in the 1978 Constitution to actively promote gender equality. These changes included decriminalizing contraceptives, permitting divorce and encouraging mixed schooling with no sex segregation (Valiente Fernández 2006).

Lately, at the beginning of the XXI century, a new wave of policies that touched on the rights and welfare entitlements of women was enacted during the socialist government of José Luiz Rodríguez Zapatero (2004-2011). These new policies embodied most of the more established principles and claims of the women's movement. Eradicating gender-based violence, fostering women's access to power and guaranteeing women's right to pregnancy termination, became policy goals in the hands of new bureaucracies and high-ranked public officials (Calvo Borobia 2014).

These rapid advances in the political arena have been similarly reflected in gender-related research and scientific publications. In recent decades, women's studies and gender have gone from a peripheral place to be considered a fundamental part of the academic community (Gartzia y Lopez-Zafra 2014).

Our search confirmed that Gender Studies constitutes a discipline itself in Spain. Several journals owned by a large number of gender research units have developed a prominent specialization in this area with high performance scores of scientific publications. Besides, we found studies addressing gender concepts with a subsidiary gender perspective, but rather a central focus on disciplines such as Sociology, Psychology, Political Science, Economics or Anthropology. Authors who are benchmarks in their subfields were also identified. Gracia Trujillo is an expert in the sexuality area, Sirin Adlbi Sibai in Islamic feminism, Alicia Puleo in ecofeminism, and Octavio Salazar in new masculinities studies.

In terms of the feminist perspectives, two most salient approaches can be identified in the Spanish literature. On one hand, a structuralist/poststructuralist feminism that focus on the structural causes and factors triggering gender inequality in Spain, such as the dominant patriarchist and androcentric order in different sectors or even the capitalist organization of work that put on the women the heaviest burden. On the other hand, a sort of institutionalist feminist perspective is identified in several studies that emphasize the formal and informal incentives, agencies, public policies, laws and institutions that influence on gender equality.

All in all, the gender concepts identified in the theoretical discussions can be bounded into nine themes which are showed in Table 1. We detected gender concepts related to anti-feminism such as 'misogyny' or 'manosphere'. In the articles that address how economic crisis has deepened gender equality, concepts such as 'feminization of poverty' or 'feminist economy' stand out. A battery of research is also focused in Education, namely through the concept 'education for equality'. We have found very specific concepts to refer to gender-based violence, such as 'Intimate Partner Violence Against Women (IPVAW)'. 'Intersectionality' is the core concept in our literature to address the connection between feminism and multiculturalism. Regarding sexualities, 'gender roles' and 'sexual hierarchy' are the most used concepts. We gathered as well several that allude to work-life balance ('female labour stress', 'feminization of care-work', among others). In the following lines, some of these concepts are further discussed in light of how these aspects have shifted over time.

Table 1. Gender concepts identified in the literature review

Theme	Theoretical gender concepts
Anti-feminism	Antifeminism, mansphere, popular misogyny, antifeminist resistance
Economic crisis	Gender inequality, gender roles, feminization of poverty, feminist economy, gender equality policies
Education	Education for equality, co-education, patriarchalism
Female leadership	Gender stereotypes, gender roles, female empowerment, glass ceiling, gender gap, gender imbalance, gender bias, androcentrism
Gender violence	Femicide, mainstream pornography, second-order sexual harassment (SOSH), intimate partner violence against women (IPVAW)
Multiculturalism	Genderization of islamophobia, intersectionality, patriarchal structure
Masculinities	Hegemonic masculinities, new masculinities, femininity
Sexualities	Sexual hierarchy, queer feminist policies, identity, LGBT political groups, gender roles.
Work-life balance	Female citizenship, female labour stress, equal distribution of care, sexual division of labour, feminization of care-work.

Withing the theme ‘female leadership’, we found a set of articles emphasizing the sectors where equality has not been achieved yet, employing concepts as ‘glass ceiling’, ‘gender stereotypes’, or ‘female empowerment’. In these pieces, it is highlighted, for instance, the considerably minor presence of women among entrepreneurs (Sabater Fernández 2018), and the greater obstacles women still have to be equal among their pairs in different areas such as science (Estradé 2022; Samper-Gras 2022), and to access to high-level executives seats (Biedma Ferrer 2017; Medina-Vicent 2021).

In terms of LGBT political groups and sexual identities, Spain has gone through very important changes in the last decades as far as gender and sexual rights are concerned. Spain is in the vanguard of sexual and gender rights recognition. In 2005, some changes in the Civil Code allowed gay and lesbians couples to marry and full adoption rights were also granted. In 2007, a ground-breaking sexual identity allowed transgender people to change their ID without the intervention of surgery. New reproductive rights have also been approved in the form of new assisted reproduction and abortion laws (Calvo y Trujillo 2011). In recent times, and surely motivated by the achievement in the field of policy making, Spanish LGTB groups are strengthening new priorities as homo, lesbo and transphobias within the education systems, and discrimination in employment and health.

Regarding masculinities, the Spanish reference authors (Salazar Benítez 2012) point out that there are some changes that are more socially accepted because they affect the role and values associated with aspects that are more obviously open to criticism. These are

changes that can be considered more superficial and that partially reform hegemonic masculinity. For instance, affectivity, emotions, social roles, and violence. However, more recent research conducted with both young and adult men finds that the rejection of issues associated with femininity (vulnerability, care, non-productive aspects, etc.) remains at the core of hegemonic masculinities (Avidad y López 2020; Lashayas et al, Goikoetxea, y Ruiz 2023) .

In relation with ‘genderization of islamophobia’, the Syrian-Spanish political scientist, Sirin Adlbi Sibai, is a reference author on the intersection between feminism, coloniality and islamophobia in Spain. She underscores the impossibility of thinking and resisting the Arab-Muslim patriarchy without doing it simultaneously of the Western-centric colonial patriarchy, and without starting from the dismantling of its structures of domination that are transversal to the structures of male domination in the current Arab-Muslim societies (Adlbi Sibai 2017).

4. Gender-based violence and work-life balance in the eyes of the literature

Above all, our systematic literature review allowed us to identify relevant gender-based needs and demands upon two central issues that predominated in the search: gender-based violence suffered by women, in different forms and manifestations, and strongly associated with models of hegemonic masculinities,- and the women’s struggle to reach work-life balance, not only affected by the gender roles and sexual division of work, but also intertwined with cross-cutting variables such as social class, race, age, immigration, territorial divisions, etc.

4.1 Gender-based violence

Gender-based violence is suffered by women on a subtle of different conditions in the Spanish context, embracing a set of issues associated to security policies. In this regard, we can find in the contributions an attempt to include the intersectional perspective under which it is necessary to analyze, dynamically and in context, how variables such as race, social status, age, etc. interact and affect subjects’ symbolic and material positioning in relation to gender-based violence (Crenshaw 1989).

Within this umbrella, we find articles addressing micro policy issues regarding domestic intra-partner violence (Bosch-Fiol y Ferrer-Perez 2019), but also symbolic and economic violence suffered by women in conditions of disability (García-Santesmases y Pié Balaguer 2017), social exclusion (Damonti y Leache 2020), etc. It is also addressed the second-order violence exerted over witnesses of gender-based violence cases (Melgar et al. 2021).

Two kinds of root causes are identified in the literature for explaining this issue. On the one hand, those that outline structural or systemic factors such as the material circumstances that force women to initiate an abuse relationship, the absence of family and social support, and an environment that tends not to censure gender violence (Damonti y Leache 2020). Furthermore, this issue is associated as well with studies of

masculinities. These articles find a relationship between gender-based violence and hegemonic masculinities. They suggest that the non-development of basic emotional abilities by men, while connected with their gender socialization, requires particular attention for the purpose of treatment and prevention of violence against women (Ferrer-Pérez y Bosch-Fiol 2016; Delgado y Viejo 2017)

On the other hand, a second explanation places the focus on the actors, fundamentally the government, who is not properly regulating situations that require a more specific legislation and investment of public resources. For instance, there are low reporting rates of legal complaints previous to a femicide taking place, because frequently the victims of intimate partner violence against women do not always have an adequate understanding of what abuse is, nor are they aware of the risk they are running (Bosch-Fiol y Ferrer-Perez 2019). This demands an effort to emphasize on education prevention programs directed both women and men raising awareness and promoting the existence of a social and legal sanction (Damonti y Leache 2020). It is also generally highlighted the need to add to the public discussion the intersection of gender with other variables of discrimination, making invisible, for example, the vulnerability of undocumented immigrant women to gender-based violence, as well as their dilemmas in denouncing their aggressors caused by the fear of deportation (Rodríguez 2011).

4.2 Work-life balance

Despite of the set of gender equality policies launched in Spain between 2004 and 2011, Spanish women are still forced to make difficult decisions when it comes to balance family and professional life (Calvo Borobia 2014). Indeed, several of the analysed contributions point out that the combination of a faulted implementation of these policies plus the 2008 financial crisis and the COVID-19 pandemic's consequences, is still pushing women away from full citizenship and, thus, jeopardizing gender equality in Spain.

A major concern of researchers is the connection between work-life balance policies and gender equality. This area embraces a set of issues associated to both family and labour market policies. These studies namely claim for the shared co-responsibility in the domestic and family chores and more flexible forms of work organization. All of the them emphasize the need to fully recognize the elderly and children's family carer not as a caregiver but as a worker, with decent social and labour rights and conditions (Peterson 2015). In addition, the unrecognition of caregiving cross-cut with other forms of social inequality. The unequal distribution of care between men and women in family environments, together with the limitation of social protection systems, put the burden of care in women of different generations, from different socioeconomic strata, from marginalized ethnic groups or from different countries of the so-called "third world", generally older, poorer and migrants women (Aguilar Idáñez 2010; Muñoz Terrón y Martín Palomo 2013; Moré 2020).

One of the most outstanding issue in this regard is the use and regulation of the parental leaves. Spain is the only country in the EU where parental leave is equal for men and women, it is non-transferable, individual, paid at 100% and its extension goes far beyond the minimum required by the EU. Nonetheless, concerns are still posed by scholars. A couple of authors underscore the need to avoid that taking either full or part-time parental leaves adds to the motherhood penalty in wages (Dominguez-Folgueras, González, y Lapuerta 2022). Besides, the co-responsible use of leaves between men and women should continue to be encouraged according to the literature, in order to prevent gender and class bias (Castellanos-Serrano 2023).

Lastly, another need detected in the literature review is the one related to the working time. The Hispanic culture of long working hours without flexibility and the limited provision of public services for childcare increase female job stress (León Llorente 2016) and add an additional burden on their extra domestic work, as well as a constraint on their career development (Altuzarra Artola, Gálvez Gálvez, y González Flores 2018).

5. Conclusions

Until 2008, claims that Spain constituted a referent of progress in relation to gender became rather popular (Gartzia y Lopez-Zafra 2014). Nevertheless, a stream of literature, more sociological in nature, notes that gender equality achievements were quite affected by the 2008 financial crisis collapse. In general, all these references suggest that the austerity policies applied after the 2008 implied a refeminization of care work (San José 2014), delayed reintegration of women into the job market and increased violence against women (Beteta Martín 2013; Martínez Guirao y Téllez Infantes 2016).

Additionally, since 2018 to the present, the gender equality levels achieved in Spain are being threatened by an anti-feminist counter-wave orchestrated mainly by the radical populist right and other movements such as cyber-antifeminisms and religious antifeminisms. While during the previous decade, Spanish antifeminism had a marked Catholic character (Cornejo-Valle y Pichardo 2018), the emergence of a radical right-wing party such as Vox and its open questioning of the Gender Violence Law represents a turning point. Accordingly, we can find studies which aim to draw an in-depth analysis of antifeminist discourses and practices, including cyberbullying and cyberviolence in social networks (Bonet-Martí 2020), as well as the analysis of those internet forums in which strategies of cyberbullying against feminists are shared, or support is given to rapists (Bonet-Martí 2021). The literature is also addressing the relevance of gender in Vox's discourse and political strategy. Gender has allowed Vox to establish its identity, a distinctively masculinist one, and to differentiate itself from competing parties. The antifeminist reaction of the rising radical-right shows that feminism holds a significant legitimacy and that Vox perceives a threat to its authoritarian and nativist project (Cabezas 2022).

To sum up, this literature review confirmed that gender is present both in the social discussion and in the academic realm. In the public-policy field, Spain is an example of

rapid change in terms of gender and reproductive rights. The current left-wing coalition government has actually enacted a battery of cutting-edge policies such as the menstruation leaves, reduction of VAT on menstrual products, the trans and LGTBI rights law, among others. Nevertheless, the research studies we have gathered show that is still necessary to improve and protect gender-based needs and demands from, on the one hand, the consequences of the economic crisis and the pandemic and, on the other hand, the advance of the anti-feminist reactions, often portrayed by the populist radical right, whose policies proposals represents a backlash for the Spanish women's rights

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